

SYNTHESIS OF SOME DIARYLSULPHONES

By A. B. SEN AND A. K. ROY

Several diarylsulphones have been prepared by the application of the Fries rearrangement and the Friedel-Crafts reaction, with a view to testing them for their antibacterial activity.

The importance of hydroxydiarylsulphones as useful antiseptics (cf. Amin, Desai, Parekh and Venkataraman, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, **13B**, 181) has encouraged the authors to undertake the synthesis of several hydroxy- and methoxy-diarylsulphones.

Much work has been done in this series by Rittler (D.R.P. 532403/1930), Simons, Archer and Rendall (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 485), Aleykuty and Baliah (this *Journal*, 1954, **32**, 513) and Amin *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) who obtained these sulphones by the Fries migration of the corresponding sulphonic esters of the phenol as well as by the Friedel and Crafts reaction between the sulphonyl chlorides and the aromatic hydrocarbons (cf. Beckerts and Otto, *Ber.*; 1878, **11**, 2066; Witt and Uermenye, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 306; Rittler, D. R. P. 555409/1931).

In the present investigation the authors have synthesised a few sulphones by the Fries rearrangement of the toluenesulphonic esters of *ortho*- and *para*-halogenated and alkyl phenols. The esters were obtained by the addition of 10% aqueous solution of caustic soda to a solution of the phenol and the sulphonyl chloride in acetone.

It was, however, observed that the rearrangement was successfully effected only in two cases, viz., (1) 6-chloro-3-methylphenyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate and (2) 2:4-dichlorophenyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate, and completely failed in other esters even under varying conditions (*i. e.* in nitrobenzene solution even at higher temperature). The product obtained by the Fries rearrangement of the ester (1), when coupled with 2:4-dichlorobenzenediazonium chloride, furnished an orange dye which could not be methylated by dimethyl sulphate in presence of acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate. The dye therefore has the chelated *o*-hydroxy-azo structure, and hence, it is beyond doubt that the *p*-toluenesulphonyl group migrates to the position *para* to the hydroxy group in this case. The ester (2) afforded the *ortho*-substituted sulphone, the *para* position being occupied.

The sulphones, which could not be prepared by the Fries rearrangement of their corresponding sulphonic esters, were obtained by the Friedel and Crafts reaction.

Four sulphones (No. 1, 2, 3 & 4, Table III) were prepared by the action of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride on the methyl ethers of the corresponding phenols in carbon disulphide in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The substitution in No. 1, 2 and 3 was in the *ortho* position to the methoxy group, as the *para* positions in these compounds were not free. The substitution in the compound No. 4 was assigned in the *para* position as one of the *ortho* positions to the methoxy group was not free and the other one was hindered.

The rest of the sulphones (No. 5-8, Table II) were obtained by the condensation of ethylbenzene and *p*-*sec*-amylbenzene with *p*-chlorobenzenesulphonyl chloride and *p*-methoxybenzenesulphonyl chloride in the same manner. In all the above cases, *para*-substituted sulphones were obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

Phenolic Esters of p-Toluenesulphonyl Chloride.—The esters were prepared by adding an aqueous 10% caustic soda solution dropwise with constant stirring to a solution of the phenol (1 mole) and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (1.1 mole) in acetone until the mixture was slightly alkaline. After this the mixture was stirred for half an hour, cooled and filtered. The crystals, thus obtained, were recrystallised from alcohol. The melting point, yield and analysis of the esters obtained are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I
[T denotes *p*-toluenesulphonate].

No.	Ester.	M.P.	Yield.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	4- <i>tert</i> -Butylphenyl-T	112°	62%	10.36	10.52
2.	4- <i>tert</i> -Amylphenyl-T	51°	65	9.92	10.06
3.	6-Chloro-3-methylphenyl-T	99-100°	63	10.47	10.80
4.	2-Diphenyl-T	65°	60	9.68	9.87
5.	4-Diphenyl-T	175-76°	68	9.71	9.87
6.	2-Chloro-4- <i>tert</i> -butylphenyl-T	90-91°	72	9.23	9.46

Fries Rearrangement of the Esters.—The Fries migration of the esters was carried out in the following way. The ester (1 M) was dissolved in CS₂ (30 c. c.) and after addition of AlCl₃ (anhyd., 1.5 M) was refluxed over a steam-bath for an hour. CS₂ was then distilled off and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 120° for an hour. After cooling, the solid was decomposed with ice-cold HCl. The crude solid was filtered off and crystallised from dilute alcohol.

It was found that only one of the above esters, viz., No. 3 and 2:4-dichlorophenyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate, underwent rearrangement, while in the other five cases the esters were recovered, unchanged. Even when the Fries migration was carried out in nitrobenzene solution at higher temperatures (120°-140°), these five esters remained unchanged as such, only the following two sulphones were obtained (Table II).

TABLE II

No.	Sulphones.	M.P.	Yield.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	4-Hydroxy-5-chloro-2-methylphenyl <i>p</i> -tolyl-	276°	40%	10.60	10.80
2.	2-Hydroxy-3:5-dichlorophenyl- <i>p</i> tolyl-	152°	50	9.80	10.16

2:4-Dichlorobenzene-azo-2-hydroxy-3'-chloro-6'-methylphenyl-5''-*p*-tolylsulphone.—2:4-Dichloroaniline was diazotised in the usual way and then coupled in the cold with a solution of 4-hydroxy-5-chloro-2-methylphenyl-*p*-tolylsulphone in caustic soda. On

acidification a solid was obtained which was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 123°. (Found: N, 5.69. $C_{20}H_{15}O_3N_2Cl_3S$ requires N, 5.96 per cent).

The eight sulphones in Table III were prepared by the Friedel-Crafts reaction, using CS_2 as the solvent.

TABLE III

No.	Phenol ether & hydrocarbon.	Sulphone.	M.P.	Yield.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>p</i> - <i>tert</i> -Butylphenyl-methyl ether	2-Methoxy-5- <i>tert</i> -butylphenyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl.	98°	45%	9.92	10.06
2.	<i>p</i> -Methoxydiphenyl	2-Methoxy-5-phenylbenzene- <i>p</i> -tolyl.	172°	60	9.06	9.45
3.	<i>p</i> - <i>tert</i> -Amylphenyl-methyl ether.	2-Methoxy-5- <i>tert</i> -amylphenyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl.	125°	52	9.22	9.63
4.	3-Methyl-6- <i>tert</i> -butylphenylmethyl ether	4-Methoxy-5- <i>tert</i> -butyl-2-methylphenyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl.	100°/4mm. (B.P.)	42	9.32	9.63
5.	Ethylbenzene	4-Ethylphenyl- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl.	8°	55	11.26	11.23
6.	<i>sec</i> -Amylbenzene	4- <i>sec</i> -Amylphenyl- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl.	77°	53	9.75	10.00
7.	Ethylbenzene	4-Ethylphenyl- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl.	110°	48	9.93	10.03
8.	<i>sec</i> -Amylbenzene	4- <i>sec</i> -Amylphenyl- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl.	148°	53	11.10	11.40

*Friedel-Crafts Reaction between the Methyl Ethers of the Phenol and *p*-Toluenesulphonyl Chloride*—The sulphones (No. 1-4, Table III) were prepared by dissolving the corresponding phenol ether (1 M) and the *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (1.1M) in 30 c.c. of CS_2 and then adding $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 1.5 M) gradually. The reaction started immediately with the evolution of HCl fumes. After the addition of $AlCl_3$, the mixture was refluxed for one hour, CS_2 distilled off and the aluminium complex decomposed with ice and HCl. The solid obtained after filtration was recrystallised from alcohol and water.

*Friedel-Crafts Reaction between the Aromatic Hydrocarbons and *p*-Methoxybenzenesulphonyl Chloride*—The sulphones (No. 5 & 6, Table III) were obtained by the action of *p*-methoxybenzenesulphonyl chloride (1.1M) on ethylbenzene (1 M) and *p*-*sec*-amylbenzene (1 M) in CS_2 (30 c.c.) in presence of $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 1.5 M) by the same procedure. The *p*-methoxybenzenesulphonyl chloride was obtained by the method used by Morgan and Cretchen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 375).

*Friedel-Crafts Reaction between the Aromatic Hydrocarbons and *p*-Chlorobenzenesulphonyl Chloride*—The sulphones (No. 7 & 8, Table III) were obtained by the same procedure as above except that *p*-chlorobenzenesulphonyl chloride was used in place of *p*-methoxybenzenesulphonyl chloride. The former was obtained by the method used by Ullmann and Korselt (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 742).